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DEVELOPMENT OF A REAL-TIME WEED DETECTION SYSTEM USING SMART GLASSES

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Kurapia (improved *Lippia nodiflora*), a ground-cover plant, is environmentally friendly and widely used in parks and gardens. However, weeds that grow in shaded areas can hinder its growth, requiring continuous removal. Manually distinguishing Kurapia from weeds is difficult, and visual inspection alone has limitations. In our previous study, we developed a smartphone application that identifies weeds from images using YOLOv5 and displays bounding boxes around them. This research aims to implement the same functionality on smart glasses to enable real-time detection and provide visual assistance for efficient weeding operations. The smart glasses used in this study were VUZIX M400, and the system was developed using Android Studio. The YOLOv5 model trained for 200 epochs was employed for weed detection. When the built-in camera captures an image, it is converted into a JPEG byte array and sent to the server via a POST request. The server performs detection using YOLOv5 and returns a result image URL in JSON format. The smart glasses then display the result image through a WebView interface. A continuous execution program was implemented to achieve real-time visual feedback resembling video output. Experimental results showed that the system successfully detected weeds from images containing both Kurapia and weeds, with bounding boxes displayed correctly. Each processing cycle required approximately 250 ms, equivalent to 4 fps. Some visual lag was observed, mainly caused by data transmission between the device and the server. In future work, we plan to optimise image resolution and detection accuracy to shorten communication time. This improvement is expected to enhance real-time performance and usability in practical weeding environments, and the system also has potential applications for detecting other plant species.

Keywords: Smart glasses, Weed detection, YOLOv5, Image processing, Real-time system

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